

This little story is instructive because from it, a tremendous insight is derived. The Army basically functions in two milieus, garrison and field. Field Training Exercises, where units go out and rehearse for battle, are very realistic, and except for dud versus live ammunition (and sometimes, not even that distinction) represents the Army in combat. The Army also does a lot of what it does in FTXs in garrison (personnel reports, ordering parts, running orders, etc.). From the Army perspective then, what you do in garrison, you do on FTXs and, by extension, in combat. So here we have soldiers reflecting the technology and productivity gains available in the civilian sector, using PCs in garrison, doing file transfers, e-mail and data base exchanges on MILNET (unclassified military DDN); a TCP/IP network. Now if in garrison troops use the Internet to do their work, what would you expect them to use in the field? TCP/IP networking software. Particularly since every one they want to talk to is on the Internet, and you get the software free for buying a computer. We expect TCP/IP to be around for a while notwithstanding the GOSIP dictum. The approach we're taking is to engineer a device that will operate in both environments and be operator or maintainer selectable. Those of you familiar with the guidance presented in the "Orange Book" of the

National Computer Security Center (NCSC), must by this time be speculating what those user PCs running around in the field are rated at (trust wise). "Trust" is the name the NCSC gives to the notion of a computer segregating users by clearance, need to know, design and other factors to insure one user not having access to another users files. The ratings go from D (unrated, bad) to A (the best). Virtually all PCs bought under unit funds and in the field today are unrated, or "D".

The Army has recognized the need for a central office to collate the computer PC and workstation (WS) requirements of the different user communities into a least common denominator and act as a central purchasing agent to acquire, at best cost, those PCs and workstations. The Project Manager so designated is titled "Common Hardware, Software" or PM, CHS. These CHS-1 PCs and WSs are, too, rated as "D" machines. The CHS PM is in the process of collating requirements for the next generation of workstations, titled CHS-2. The trust level of these machines will probably be C-2. It turns out that the Intell/EW functional area has trust requirements exceeding the level of most of the rest of the Army. They will probably acquire the DIA sponsored Compartmented Mode Work Station (CMWS) which is expected to be a B-2 machine. See fig. 2.

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You can see how the Army will have a proliferation of machines at various "trust" levels. The design of our intended Internet Security Device must take that into account. This is more than just a "nice to have". A different security device for different trust level machines would create a proliferation of stock numbers, with attendant different training courses, different maintenance courses, proliferation of spare parts, different accounting and possibly different MOSs to use and repair it. These are lifecycle cost drivers. Economy dictates one device to service all.

One approach the Army might take is as follows: Remember we wish to keep the device certifiable by NSA. Remember also that we need to interface to a number of data terminal equipments (DTEs). As long as we're at it, let's make it amenable to interface to a number of data communications equipments (DCEs) on the BLACK side as well. The DTE, DCE specific interfaces could be cards or personality software running in the goal device (herein titled Tactical End-to-end Encryption Device or TEED). What NSA would certify is the power supply/mother board/ Network Security Kernel (K), in the TEED. The interface boards might be off the shelf or developed at government expense hardware or software (or combination of) whichever is most likely to get certified. See fig 3.

We touched lightly on computers in FTXs, what experience do we have in actual combat? We do have very recent experience and lessons learned via Desert Shield/Desert Storm. The first, which should be no surprise, is that we like to confront and engage the enemy with allies. Any approach to security must take this into account. This is easy to say, hard to do, as to NSA, cryptographic technology of the type 1 class is considered a national treasure as it protects national secrets from release to unauthorized parties. NSA is (rightly so) not amenable to sharing too many family jewels with foreign powers. Army thinks a fair position would be to at least be interoperable with NATO or select NATO allies. This could have impact on cryptokey management procedures invoked. Our device may, in fact, have to work in two modes: US and Allied.

The Army would like to see more BLACK key in the field and the extension of the "unclassified when unkeyed" concept ala STU-3s. In fact de-centralized keying, as popularized by the STU-3s is very attractive. Yet, the Army, possible more than any other service, communicates in a very hierarchical manner. One outcome of this is that we're exploring the concept of limiting connectivity based on "need lines" to see if that will help the Accreditation process.

Fig. 3 Possible TEED Approach

At this point let me digress for a moment to speak to the paradox of securing (in the military sense) of "open systems". The thrust of "open systems" is the notion of universal connectivity, shared resources, access to remote data bases, remote job entry, etc. the idea of security is to only communicate with those you are authorized to communicate with and, at that, exchanging only the minimum essential data to get a job done. It could be thought of as two horses pulling a plow in opposite directions. The important point here is that, from the Army point of view, you don't need to casually talk to every other soldier in the Army. In fact, the list of people you might initiate sessions with is probably small. On the other hand, the dynamics of the battlefield being what they are, such pre-judgement of need lines based on think-tank wargaming may actually harm the soldier's ability to carry out his mission. This continues to be an area of investigation.

Back now to "lessons learned". Two observations were that once troops were deployed, and their functions and clearance put them on the SECRET high MSE packet network, they had no way of getting back to unclassified mainframe hosts (remember in the basements of buildings)? Because as SECRET high, they could not go beyond their network security perimeter. Those troops deployed whose functions didn't allow them access to the MSE communications resource (users exchanging unclassified data), could not use the MSE to traverse messages to other users either on the MSE or anywhere else. This means that 1) users in the field were precluded from doing business as they had become used to and 2) a duplicative communications resource to serve the unclassified community was needed. This pretty much stems from the notion that if you have a SECRET high network, it has to be protected from the UNCLAS world. A remote job entry request from the UNCLAS world could very well be a bad guy attempting attacks on network resources. To combat this, one needs a very strong authentication feature. If developed and implemented, it would save the cost of a redundant network. Now that we're in the mode of thinking about security attributes, let's explore them further.

SECURITY ATTRIBUTES

In determining what security attributes our box might have, it would be instructive to review the threats as we see them. Threats arise to the information transmitted out of the TEED, as well as to the TEED itself. These divide into three categories as passive attacks, active attacks and tampering. Under passive attacks we find eavesdropping (passive surveillance of network channels to discern information), traffic analysis (collection, analysis and interpretation of communications patterns) and emanations attack (collection, analysis and interpretation of electromagnetic emissions). Under active attacks we can list unauthorized connection attempts (intruder attempts to establish a network connection using a false identity or reply of a previous, legitimate message), message stream modification (attempt to reorder, modify, delete information) and denial of network service (preventing or delaying legitimate use of network services). Under tampering we list damage (could be accidental or intentional), substitution (introducing an unauthorized, malicious component), theft (bad guys may pay for a model) and probing (to extract traffic keys or explore details of sensitive technology). Covert channels are yet another threat, straddling the passive/active categories as it depends on the mechanisms of covert channel signalling.

To combat these threats, traditional security services, as articulated in guidance documents include: Data Confidentiality, Data Integrity, Authentication, Access Control and Non-Repudiation. A number of other features are of interest to the Army either in support of the traditional security services or in their own right such as: Availability (is the TEED and network going to be ready to service the attached workstation when it is needed), Gradual Release (gradual introduction of this asset into a network (may not be able to deliver enough TEEDs at one time to completely populate a network), Labeling (to both be capable of preserving labels passed to it by a "B" rated machine, and to append labels to session traffic as declared by the authorized user at time of initiation),

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Object Reuse (all storage objects in the TEED shall insure that no data resides before granting usage), Trusted Path (to support the communications path between the TEED and the user's workstation), MLS Goal (the affordable "MLS" path is to allow for a number of levels available to a given user, at any time he needs it (at the convenience of the user!). True MLS would provide for multiple windows open on a display, each at a different security level. This would cost a lot of money, not just in certifying the security device, but for the workstation as well. TEED is expected to support "Security Session Processing" on all rated machines.

Are there any other considerations, perhaps not Army specific that we might be interested in? What are some good network security engineering practices anyway? On a network basis, experienced users are used to a variety of service including remote job entry. From a security perspective, it makes sense to limit what privileges a remote user would have on a machine. Better if you could incorporate some sort of query/response type system in lieu of remote logins (delete TELNET service). The book "The Coo-coo's Egg" relates how some hackers in West Germany were able to enter DOD computers via remote login on the internet. After rummaging files these hackers could erase all evidence in the computer that they had been there. They could have just as easily erased or modified data, with serious repercussions.

For simplicity, cost and certificating, TEED is envisioned as a single user device. In the tactical Army, most computer data users are in fact working off of single workstations, so that requirement is not at all onerous.

Army computer data operation consists of islands of ethernet LANs connected to each other via packet switches using UHF radio shots for dispersion. These radio links are, while suitable for voice traffic, not as good for data. Remember these circuits were designed to carry voice traffic, which is much more tolerant of errors than data. Whereas the networking protocols guarantee error free delivery, we may wish to engineer more fault tolerant protocols to keep retransmissions at a minimum. Also,

in view of the limited bandwidth the Army tactical battlefield provides, investigations of "multicast" protocol headers and maximum use of User Datagram Protocol (UDP) is favored.

The most distinguishing characteristic of tactical computer networking is the movement, fluidity and resultant constant reconfiguration of the network. Current TEEDs do not support the dynamic nature of this network, ergo the development effort we are beginning now.

The generic name given to the tactical Army approach is ASTI, standing for Army Secure Tactical Initiative. I've already discussed some of the attributes of the Tactical End-to-end Encryption Device, or TEED. Some of the other jobs foreseen under ASTI are: Secure Gateway (SEGAT), Secure Authentication (SECUSA) and Trusted Network Base (TNB). The objectives of the devices can be synopsized as follows:

TEED: Develop a tactical internet security device that allows for Multiple levels of security and end-to-end encryption. Provides all traditional (and some unique) network level security services. Currently envisioned as an applique that resides between the workstation and the communications media.

SEGAT: Develop a "BLACK" gateway between the MSE Packet Network and DDN and allies. Also to develop an "algorithm translator" so that different Army security schemes might talk to each other directly.

SECUSA: develop user friendly (user acceptable) network based authentication schemes.

TNB: specify, develop and implement a set of technologies to assure network based security throughout the various network components (workstations, TEEDs, gateways, switches) and software (key management, secure network monitoring, secure applications).

I've attempted to give a feeling for why the Army (tactical guys) approaches network security the way it does. The following papers will get into more of the implementations of the ideas discussed here.

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